

EOOSC-IF

Guidance note: Assigning an Interoperability Guideline to an EOOSC Service Profile

Version 1.0
May 2023

EOSC-IF / Guidance note: Assigning an Interoperability Guideline to an EOSC Service Profile

Lead by **GÉANT**
Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT)

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

This document provides additional guidance for users that would like to assert that an EOSC Service supports an EOSC Interoperability Guideline as registered in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V0.1	April 2023	Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT)	First draft
V1.0	May 2023	Michelle Williams (GÉANT)	Final Version published to Zenodo

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the EOSC Future Consortium is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#). The EOSC Future project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020, Grant Agreement number 101017536.

Table of Contents

Glossary	1
List of Abbreviations	1
1 Introduction	2
2 Types of Interoperability Guideline	2
3 How Assign an Interoperability Guideline to an EOSC Service Profile	2
4 Related documents	4
References	4

Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JQCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework

1 Introduction

The EOSC-IF will be built upon a wide range of components, such as standards, APIs, policy frameworks, etc. Starting with human-readable interoperability guidelines that aim to promote and facilitate interoperability across services, resources, infrastructures and domains, the Framework will begin to incorporate more executable, machine-readable artefacts that would support composable or executable workflows at a later stage. Guidance notes for writing an EOSC Interoperability Guideline for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework are provided¹.

Interoperability Guidelines that meet the [Inclusion Criteria](#)² can be onboarded to the EOSC Portal using the EOSC Providers Portal.

The EOSC Interoperability Registry allows Providers to onboard a description of the Interoperability Guideline that contains references to the relevant documentation, APIs, protocols, etc that the Guideline recommends. The description 'record' that results from the onboarding procedure is called an 'Interoperability Guideline Profile'.

When onboarded, an Interoperability Guideline can be assigned to an EOSC Service Profile, which allows the Provider to declare that it supports the specified Interoperability Guideline.

2 Types of Interoperability Guideline

An **EOSC-Core Interoperability Guideline** describes specifications for the purposes of interoperating resources with EOSC-Core services. EOSC-Core guidelines provide context and description in order to provide technical instructions to scientific resource providers that would like to integrate their services and/or resources with (or be interoperable with) one or more EOSC-Core Services. These guidelines are created by operators of EOSC-Core Services to provide guidance to scientific service and resource providers who wish to benefit from the functionalities that the EOSC-Core services offer.

An **EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guideline (thematic/community)** refers to where thematic or community services and resources interoperate with each other, usually at a domain level such as Cluster-specific. These guidelines are created by scientific community experts to provide guidance to their communities and highlight the importance of their interoperability efforts at the European-wide EOSC level. They are further intended to increase awareness of the existing thematic and community accomplishments to facilitate/increase interoperability relating to specific domains.

An **EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guideline (horizontal)** refers to where services and resources interoperate with each other across communities and infrastructures. These are important at the EOSC Exchange level to help EOSC facilitate cross-linking of services and resources while staying domain-agnostic. These are of wider applicability than the thematic/horizontal guidelines and have a much broader scope. These guidelines are created by scientific community experts to provide guidance to their own community and highlight their importance at the European-wide EOSC level. However, this, similarly, makes them more difficult to develop and requires cross-Cluster engagement and representation to ensure they are well-rounded and widely applicable to a diverse range of intended guideline users.

3 How to Assign an Interoperability Guideline to an EOSC Service Profile

Please note, it is assumed that the service already has an EOSC Service Profile within the EOSC Providers Portal and has administration rights for the related Service Profile. If not, please refer to further instructions in the EOSC Provider Hub for creating such a Profile.

¹ Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929870

² <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria>

Instruction	Detail
Navigate to the EOSC Providers Portal	<p>providers.eosc-portal.eu/home</p>
<p>Select My Providers</p> <p>Select the Relevant Provider</p> <p>Select the Service Profile that requires the assignment of an Interoperability Guideline</p>	
<p>The 'Assign Guidelines' option can be selected from inside the Provider dashboard.</p>	
<p>The Provider can assign as many approved Interoperability Guidelines to its Service Profile as are required (note that it is also possible to remove an assigned guideline from a Service Profile by clicking the X next to the item in the list).</p>	

When Interoperability Guidelines are assigned to an EOSC Service Profile, it is possible for users to see all of the Interoperability Guidelines that your Service supports via the EOSC Marketplace UI, and the Interoperability Guideline Profile in the EOSC Marketplace will list all services that assert its Guideline.

4 Related documents

- EPOT Procedure-14: Onboard an Interoperability Guideline (relating to EPOT team activities).³
- Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929870
- Guidance note: Reviewing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929900
- Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC: 10.5281/zenodo.7929834
- EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile Data Model

References

- [1] Eosc-portal.eu. 2021. EOSC Portal. [online] Available at: <<https://eosc-portal.eu/>>
- [2] EOSC Onboarding Inclusion Criteria, [online] Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria>
- [3] Data Cite Metadata Schema 4.4, 201 [online] Available at: DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>
- [4] EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile Data Model [online] Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Interoperability+Guideline+Profile++Data+Model>

³

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCOB/EPOT+Procedure-14%3A+Onboard+an+Interoperability+Guideline>